

The Standing Liaison Round Table (SLRT): A Collaborative Framework

- The BBioNets case -

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Abstract

Collaboration and networking among EU-funded projects are essential components to attain the goals of the European Commission's research and innovation programmes, and deliver more impactful outcomes. Envisioned and managed by the [BBioNets project](#), the Standing Liaison Round Table (SLRT) is a fundamental component of the project's collaborative efforts to attain a wider reach to its main audience, farmers and foresters, and promote Bio-Based Technologies (BBTs). It constitutes a form of 'nucleus team' that focuses on strategy and initiates specific activities within the wider partnerships cultivated by BBioNets. Selected across various destinations, partner projects are situated at the intersection of the bioeconomy and primary producers' needs. The SLRT has successfully aligned dissemination efforts across projects through coordinated social media campaigns, contribution to and promotion of each other's newsletters and significant activities, attendance at joint meetings or events, organisation of joint workshops, cross-referencing in publications, and involvement or assistance in specific activities. Its activities are expected to continue throughout the duration of the BBioNets project, with a clearly articulated expression of interest from external entities in its management following BBioNets' completion.

Introduction

The **Standing Liaison Round Table (SLRT)** is a collaboration initiative born under the [BBioNets project](#), reflecting the intent and commitment of [FOCUS STC](#), the partner leading collaborations, to establish meaningful synergies with other projects and initiatives. It is envisioned as a **wider collaboration platform** assembling projects linked in a broader way to the **two BBioNets focal points: the circular bioeconomy and primary producers**.

BBioNets is an EU-funded Thematic Network, which relies on, promotes, and further advances the work carried out by [EIP-AGRI Operational Groups](#) (OGs) with respect to the management and/or processing of agricultural and forest biomass with Bio-Based Technologies (BBTs).

Collaboration and networking are essential elements for projects funded under the European Union's research and innovation programme to blend perspectives, approaches, and expertise, and ultimately enhance knowledge exchange to the benefit of their respective audiences. Rather than a 'business as usual' approach, FOCUS STC's aim was to strive for a viable and substantive interaction format. The team's vision was to create an **enabling and structured communication environment** that would be conducive to synergies, allowing for both bilateral and multilateral collaboration, thus increasing the collective outreach of all projects involved.

Following up on the SLRT's wider acceptance and success, this publication presents the overall process of setting up the SLRT, its organisation and activities, as well as key achievements and impact. It also reflects on its future prospects and ways to ensure its continuation after BBioNets' lifespan.

Setting up the SLRT

To establish the SLRT, FOCUS STC began by compiling an initial list of projects (96) considered as valid candidates for bilateral collaboration with BBioNets. Those projects were identified by conducting a thorough search in the [EU Funding & Tenders Portal](#). Having gone through Work Programmes and discerning potentially relevant topics across various destinations, i.e. topics connected to the bioeconomy or primary producers, the team proceeded to research the proposals that had been selected for funding. An excel file was created to collect pertinent information about those projects, notably their scope and objectives, the countries represented, and a contact entity or person (Figure 1).

Acronym	Full Title	Type	Programm	Topic	GA number
NUTRI-KNOW	NUTRI-KNOW - BROADENING THE IMPACT OF EIP-AGRI OPERATIONAL GROUPS IN THE FIELD OF NUTRIENT MANAGEMENT: KNOWLEDGE EXPLOITATION AND EASY-TO-UNDERSTAND MATERIAL FOR FARMERS AND PRACTITIONERS	CSA	Horizon Europe	HORIZON-CL6-2022-GOVERNANCE-01-13	101086524
ShapingBio	Shaping the future bioeconomy across sectoral, governmental and geographical levels	CSA	Horizon Europe	HORIZON-CL6-2021-GOVERNANCE-01-04	101060252
Soil-X-Change	Fostering cross-border knowledge exchange and co-creation on sustainable soil and farm management	CSA	Horizon Europe	HORIZON-CL6-2023-GOVERNANCE-01-18	101133914
SCALE-UP	Concepts, tools and applications for community-driven bioeconomy development in European rural areas	CSA	Horizon Europe	HORIZON-CL6-2021-CIRC BIO-01-08	101060264
BRILIAN	Cooperative business models for bio-based chains in rural areas	IA	Horizon Europe	HORIZON-JU-CBE-2022-IA-02	101112436
BIO2REG	Enabling transition towards circular and systemic BIOeconomy model regions by a	CSA	Horizon Europe	HORIZON-CL6-2023-CircBio-01-10	101135420
FOREST4EU	European innovation partnership network promoting operational groups dedicated to forestry and agroforestry	CSA	Horizon Europe	HORIZON-CL6-2022-GOVERNANCE-01-13	101086216

Figure 1: Partial view of the exploratory excel file used for identifying relevant projects.

The team widely debated that even though the bioeconomy and the rural world are closely related, all bioeconomy-related projects do not specifically target or incorporate in their scope farmers and/or foresters. The same way, all projects targeting primary producers do not necessarily delve into issues

related to the bioeconomy aspect of BBioNets. To this end, **the collaboration endeavour should aim at projects situated at the intersection of both domains.**

It was also determined that in order for external projects to react positively to a collaboration query, a **satisfactory number of common elements or topics of interest** should be identified before initiating contact. An additional consideration to be taken into account was the completion phase of the projects to be approached. It was thus important to start by considering BBioNets' own cornerstones in terms of mission and objectives, and elaborating on the following elements (Figure 2):

- Pertinent key words
- Target audience
- Types of potential collaboration
- Timeline

Figure 2: Selection criteria for relevant projects.

FOCUS STC made the strategic decision to contact projects that received funding and started either **during the same period** (under the same Call) **or a year / a year and a half** (1 – 1.5 years) **before BBioNets** (recent previous Calls).

The rationale of this decision was that all projects needed to be allowed sufficient time together to mesh with one another and find an appropriate pace and pattern to deploy their collaboration. More *mature* projects could benefit from the synergy by multiplying their dissemination channels and identifying potential partners to jointly organise some of their activities. *Younger* projects could gain traction by increasing the visibility of their social media pages and website when tagging already widely known projects, while at the same time promoting news, activities and outcomes of common interest to their own audience. Both *mature* and *younger* projects would stand to benefit, all the while attaining the utmost goal of such collaboration: **greater impact** and **efficiency**.

Once all above-mentioned essential elements were satisfactorily broached and decided upon, the team proceeded with determining which of the identified projects met that initial set of criteria and should be contacted. Having reached a satisfying number of candidates, the first communication with those projects was initiated in the form of individual emails, accompanied by a one-page BBioNets presentation. As soon as bilateral meetings were arranged, a thorough search was conducted both on the CORDIS platform and the project websites to identify, as stated previously, points of common interest that could serve as a basis for collaboration. All commonalities and collaboration possibilities were recorded in individual files presented during the bilateral meetings to facilitate the discussion flow.

FOCUS STC informed project representatives of its intention to establish the SLRT and pursue further networking and multilateral cooperation among all interested parties. The initiative was warmly

welcomed and all representatives expressed their willingness to participate in the “SLRT: The ‘Cooperation inaugural event’”, an online meeting for all interested projects to get acquainted and exchange collaboration ideas.

During the event organisation, there were additional projects suggested as being relevant to the common ‘*bioeconomy / primary producers*’ scope. Most were invited, aiming at the expansion of the SLRT, while making also sure that the meeting remained within a 2-hour timeframe to make it productive and accommodate all confirmed participants.

The event took place on **26th April 2024**, bringing together **29 representatives from 12 projects**, along with an EU official. It marked the beginning of an effective synergistic itinerary. Even though most projects were contacted in the early stages of BBioNets, the SLRT remains open for the admission of new projects situated at the intersection of the bioeconomy and agriculture/forestry. It could be considered as the ‘nucleus team’ of the BBioNets collaboration efforts, focusing on strategy and acting as the initiator of specific activities, within the wider networks and collaboration vision enfolded all BBioNets partnerships. The SLRT has currently reached the number of **17 partner projects**, and features a subgroup consisting of 6 EIP-AGRI Thematic Networks (BBioNets being such a Network itself).

SLRT Organisation & Activities

One of the fundamental principles of the SLRT is that **participation is voluntary and non-binding**. Once projects have joined, they have access to an **online private repository**, carefully structured by FOCUS STC to allow easy and rapid access to each other’s news, items to promote, and details pertaining to all activities. They also communicate via a **common mailing list**, sending queries for assistance, relevant notifications, and so on. For practical management considerations, each project has two designated representatives with access to the repository and the mailing list (ideally one from their D&C team to facilitate joint dissemination and communication).

The collaborative actions pursued during the first year since the establishment of the SLRT include:

- cross-promotion of established collaborations through the websites and social media channels of the respective projects;
- input to each other’s newsletters;
- dissemination of upcoming actions organised by partner projects that are of interest to each project’s specific audiences;
- promotion of news or results through press releases and website articles;
- joint social media campaigns;
- promulgation of the SLRT;
- support through the participation in the projects’ Advisory Boards, Stakeholder Panels, online or onsite events;
- exchange of information on common topics of interest;
- organisation of joint events.

Key Achievements & Impact

Even though the SLRT can testify to several forms of collaboration, it could be argued that the most prominent of its achievements in the first year of its operation are a joint **social media campaign** and the **co-organisation of a forthcoming event across Thematic Networks**.

Acting on a campaign idea proposed by a partner project, FOCUS STC managed the logistics and organisation of an SLRT online meeting, where 12 out of 14, at the time, projects agreed to run the **“BioPills” social media campaign**, aiming to spotlight how each project contributes to sustainability, innovation, and the circular economy.

Running from 21/10/2024 to 12/05/2025, the campaign shares **insights into various aspects of the bio-based industries** through a series of posts, demonstrating how the projects drive collectively positive change. The plan devised envisioned creating one post per project, with individual BioPills focusing on a specific bioeconomy topic shared across social media every two weeks on Mondays. The high level of engagement recorded highlighted the warm reception and endorsement of the campaign by both project representatives and the wider public. As a result, it was decided that the “BioPills” campaign would be renewed for a second round, launching in autumn 2025 and including all interested projects of the SLRT.

Moving ahead, the SLRT’s subgroup of Thematic Networks that promote the work of EIP-AGRI Operational Groups (OGs) is preparing to host a **joint event** under the **slogan “Collaboration in Action: Unlocking the Potential of OGs”**. The event will be entitled “The future of EIP-AGRI Operational Groups: challenges, opportunities and existing support services” and is expected to lead to the preparation of a **joint paper**.

In terms of impact, it could be argued the SLRT successfully established enhanced collaboration by creating meaningful connections and opportunities for synergy. It attained wider outreach and increased efficiency by presenting results and innovations of individual projects to a broader audience, avoiding duplication of effort. It allowed for productive cross-fertilisation, combining diverse viewpoints and expertise, and thus leading to new insights across the bioeconomy.

Future Prospects

The SLRT activities are expected to continue throughout the lifespan of the BBioNets project. FOCUS STC will keep in touch with all partner projects via the dedicated mailing list, investigating further collaboration opportunities either online or onsite. All suggestions and opportunities are welcomed, both for bilateral and multilateral synergies.

There have already been discussions held with some project representatives about the day after for the SLRT, upon completion of BBioNets. When time comes, the initiative could still be led by FOCUS STC in the framework of a new relevant project, or the torch could be inherited by a different, ongoing project. Considering the initial strategic decision to only contact projects launched within a close time range, most of the first SLRT project members will be reaching their end at that point, succeeded by the newest wave of adhesions. This could potentially require a slight re-orientation of the SLRT aims and audiences, taking into consideration the need for adaptation to new realities and objectives. Nonetheless, it is deemed crucial to avoid duplicating efforts by creating ever more networks, especially when an already established one could effectively serve as a gravitating point for new entrants in the field.

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